

DECONSOLIDATION BEHAVIOR OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS AS CORE IN SANDWICH STRUCTURE [ICCM22-I/696]

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Introduction

Deconsolidation phenomenon (so-called springback) is commonly unwanted in industry because it will lead to low part quality and even render parts useless due to the release of stress and high porosity, we adopted it as the method to make carbon fiber (CF) core in sandwich structure. Taking advantage of this high void content and lightweight feature, this kind of material is favorable to be applied as core in sandwich structure to achieve high stiffness-to-weight ratio.

By the analysis of the spring-back effect, the microstructure and the residual stress can be studied in the sandwich; and the methods for controlling the spring-back effect and the mechanism of the generation of residual stress are important not only in mechanical field but also in the production processes and applications.

In this study, the spring-back effect on a transversely isotropic short carbon fiber paper reinforced thermoplastic was investigated. And the sandwiches with different levels of deconsolidation were manufactured and compared under the macro measuring and observing. Meanwhile, the sandwich made by deconsolidated carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic core was compared with foam core sandwich.

- Decrease weight
- Increase stiffness
- Design freely
- Additional benefits

[1] <http://adventuresofgreg.com/blog/2009/04/01/ocean-boat-progress-finally/>
 [2] http://www.winddaily.com/reports/Researchers_build_a_tougher_lighter_wind_turbine_blade_999.html
 [3] <http://www.stealthcrafts.com/stealth-525.html>
 [4] <http://www.bbc.com/news/business-25833264>
 [5] <http://www.railway-technology.com/features/featurepersonal-rapid-transport-vecfus-ferrari-pininfarina/featurepersonal-rapid-transport-vecfus-ferrari-pininfarina-3.html>

Decosolidation process (spring back process)

Carbon fiber paper reinforced thermoplastic (CPT) sheet

Length of carbon fiber: 6mm
Resin fiber: Polyamide 6
Density 1.30g/cm³
Vf : 20%

The consolidated CPT samples was put on a heated metal under 265°C without constraint.

After spring-back, CPT has uniform thickness through whole plane direction, which indicates sandwich plate with smooth surface, even uniform inner stress distribution under loading can be expected.

Molding

Unidirectional carbon fiber prepreg (UD) sheet

Carbon fiber : TR50S
Resin : Polyamide 6
Density 1.51 g/cm³
Vf : 50%

Carbon fiber paper reinforced thermoplastic (CPT) sheet

Length of carbon fiber: 6mm
Resin fiber: Polyamide 6
Density 1.30g/cm³
Vf : 20%

Result and discussion

In two-step forming, the facing suffered from the thermal heating twice with the high temperature which might probably cause thermal damage on the facing and at the interface of the beam, meanwhile, in the case of One-step forming, although the designated thickness might lead to lack of pressure to mold the facings, the release of the internal fiber elastic deformation during heating on CPT sheets provide certain pressure to compact facings. And the flexural property of spring backed sandwiches show superior to foam core sandwiches.

Conclusion

- From the experiments and results analysis, the release of the internal fiber elastic deformation regarded as the main mechanism of the spring-back effect and it contributes to the consolidation of the facing.
- One-step forming process for CPT core sandwich can be considered as an efficient and reliable method when the core is designed to a suitable deconsolidation level.
- The CPT core sandwich shows superior to foam core sandwich in terms of mechanical property.